

Legal and strategic approaches to AI-enhanced critical infrastructure threats

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Abstract: Communications networks form the backbone of society in today's interconnected world, enabling global connectivity and innovation. These systems are vulnerable to cyberattacks, however, as evidenced by Russian forces targeting satellite-based networks during the Ukraine war, disrupting crucial services. This highlights the need to protect critical infrastructure from digital threats. AI-

enhanced threats exacerbate vulnerabilities but also offer defence opportunities. To fortify against disruptions, the strengthening of legal frameworks, fostering of international cooperation and leveraging of AI for defence are essential. Addressing these challenges requires a multifaceted international approach to safeguard our critical digital infrastructure from evolving cyberthreats.

Problem statement: How can critical communications infrastructure be protected from cyberattacks and AI-enhanced threats, particularly in light of the vulnerabilities exposed during the Ukraine war?

Bottom line upfront: Recent cyberattacks like those on ViaSat's KA-SAT network during the Ukraine conflict underscore the need for a global cybersecurity framework. These attacks have highlighted the fragility of communications networks. Effective cybersecurity requires a collaborative approach between the private sector and governments, focusing on advanced technologies and coordinated measures.

So what?: Governments and the private sector must collaborate to develop a comprehensive global framework to enhance cybersecurity. This should prioritize advanced encryption, AI-driven threat detection and Zero Trust principles. Establishing an international cybersecurity agency to unify policies and responses, alongside promoting cybersecurity education and public-private partnerships, is essential for building resilience to evolving threats.

Fragile connectivity faces growing cyberthreats

In today's increasingly interconnected world, the fabric of our daily lives is woven with intricate and often invisible communications threads. These threads encompass various technologies, from telecommunications networks to satellite connections, forming the essential infrastructure that supports our modern society. This critical framework facilitates global connectivity and drives continuous innovation, serving as the backbone of our daily operations and interactions.

However, much like a delicate spider's web, this infrastructure is inherently fragile and susceptible to various threats. Although physical threats have traditionally been considered the primary danger, the digital age has introduced a new and pervasive menace: cyberattacks. As the global dependence on technology grows, so does the risk of cyberattacks targeting these vital systems. These attacks, executed through the realm of bits and bytes, have the potential to disrupt, damage and dismantle the very networks on which societies worldwide rely.

In the context of the ongoing war in Ukraine Russian forces have strategically targeted communications networks dependent on satellite technology. A prominent example occurred at the outset of Russia's invasion, when a cyberattack was launched against ViaSat's KA-SAT satellite network.[1] This attack not only resulted in a significant loss of communications for the Ukrainian military but also had widespread ramifications across Europe. Thousands of users were affected, including 5,800 German wind turbines, which were rendered offline for weeks, illustrating the extent of the collateral damage caused by such cyberattacks.[2]

The Russian invasion and its accompanying cyberwarfare have underscored the critical necessity of protecting global infrastructure. A successful breach of critical infrastructure can have catastrophic consequences, with impacts on economic stability, public safety and national security. The ViaSat attack exemplifies how vulnerable interconnected systems are, and how essential services can be disrupted, highlighting the fragile nature of our technological dependencies.

The technology landscape continues to evolve rapidly. One of the most pressing concerns is the emergence of AI-enhanced threats, which have shown a marked increase in sophistication. These advanced cyberthreats pose new challenges to global efforts to secure critical infrastructure, making it imperative to stay ahead of potential vulnerabilities.

Cutting-edge technologies, robust policy frameworks and international cooperation

This evolving threat landscape necessitates a proactive approach to cybersecurity that involves the adoption of cutting-edge technologies, robust policy frameworks and international cooperation. By understanding the intricate dynamics of cyberwarfare and investing in resilient infrastructure, governments, industries and global stakeholders can better prepare to defend against these sophisticated attacks, ensuring the stability and security of our global communications networks.

The communications industry has undergone a profound transformation over the last 25 years, evolving into a complex network that integrates terrestrial, satellite and wireless systems. These components are intricately interconnected, creating a multifaceted and dynamic sector. Initially focusing primarily on providing voice services, the industry has expanded into a highly competitive and integrated field, offering diverse services. This interconnectedness means that providers across various platforms –

satellite, wireless and wireline – rely on each other to sustain and complete their traffic, often sharing facilities and technologies to ensure seamless interoperability.

The ownership and operation of most of this communications infrastructure lie within the private sector. It is therefore primarily the private sector's responsibility to ensure the protection and security of its infrastructure and assets. The complexity and interdependence of modern communications networks, however, necessitate robust collaboration with governments. Public-private partnerships are crucial in predicting, anticipating and responding to cyberthreats. Such cooperative efforts are essential for safeguarding the integrity of communications, especially during critical times. Maintaining these partnerships is vital for the immediate functioning of communications networks and understanding and mitigating the broader implications of potential disruptions. Effective collaboration ensures that national leaderships can communicate during emergencies, supports the operations of other critical sectors, and enhances the overall effectiveness of response and recovery initiatives. In an era when the technology landscape is continuously evolving, the combined efforts of both the private and public sectors are indispensable for maintaining the resilience and security of our communications infrastructure.

The vital role of communications networks

The communications sector today underpins the functionality of diverse industries, making it an indispensable pillar of modern infrastructure. This interdependence highlights the critical nature of robust and secure communications networks across various domains.[3] A prime example is the relationship between the communications and energy sectors. The energy sector supplies the power to operate cellular towers and communications facilities. Conversely, it relies on robust communications systems to efficiently monitor and control electricity delivery. Communications networks enable real-time data transmission, which is crucial for maintaining the stability and reliability of power grids and managing energy resources effectively.

Similarly, the information technology (IT) sector depends heavily on communications networks, which form the backbone of critical control systems, physical architecture and internet infrastructure. These networks are essential for distributing applications and services, ensuring that data flow seamlessly across platforms and devices. The synergy between IT and communications is vital for supporting various digital operations and innovations that drive economic growth and societal advancement.

The financial services sector also relies on secure and reliable communications networks to execute transactions and manage the operations of financial markets. The integrity and confidentiality of financial data depend on robust communications infrastructure to prevent fraud and ensure the smooth functioning of global financial systems. Secure communications are indispensable for maintaining trust and stability within the financial ecosystem.

In the realm of public safety the emergency services sector utilizes communications technologies for resource coordination, emergency responses, public alerts and handling emergency calls. Effective communication is the cornerstone of efficient emergency management, enabling quick and coordinated responses to crises, thereby saving lives and mitigating damage. The transport sector depends on communications systems to oversee and manage traffic movement across ground, sea and air routes. Communications networks facilitate the real-time exchange of information necessary for navigation, traffic control and logistics management, ensuring the safe and efficient transport of goods and passengers.

These examples underscore robust communications systems' importance as a critical infrastructure cornerstone. Given this significance, it is clear that communications systems remain a prime target for nation-state threat actors. These adversaries are increasingly leveraging the power of artificial intelligence (AI) to employ more sophisticated and stealthy techniques. AI-enhanced methods allow these actors to establish a long-term presence and evade detection more effectively, posing significant cybersecurity challenges. By harnessing AI, threat actors can automate complex tasks, refine their strategies and adapt quickly to changing security environments. This makes it increasingly difficult to protect vital systems against breaches and disruptions. The dual-use nature of certain infrastructure such as space-based communications systems serving both civilian and military purposes further amplifies the risk. Protecting these systems is paramount for ensuring national security, economic stability and public safety.

The responsibility to safeguard critical infrastructure

Yet the primary responsibility for safeguarding the infrastructure and assets of the communications sector lies with the private sector. Envision the catastrophic impact if communication systems were to fail for a day, a week or even a month. Such failures would disrupt technical operations and have

profound ripple effects across geopolitical, social, economic and psychological domains. The economy would suffer, societal functions would be hindered, national security would be compromised, and the population's psychological wellbeing would be severely affected.

The global cyberthreat landscape has dramatically evolved since Russia's most recent invasion of Ukraine.[4] More aggressive state actors now engage in hybrid warfare, blending traditional military tactics with sophisticated cyberoperations.[5] The ViaSat hack is a clear example of cyberoperations extending beyond the immediate conflict in Ukraine, with an impact on a wide range of targets. The cyber battlefield now includes social media platforms, private and public information networks, and critical infrastructure. Western companies, media and government services are increasingly being attacked, with AI utilized in various forms to enhance these assaults' sophistication and effectiveness.[6]

These hybrid threats pose a severe risk of escalating conflicts and increasing the likelihood of direct confrontations between nations. Despite the growing urgency, achieving effective cooperation among democratic governments, agencies and the private sector in the cybersecurity realm remains a significant challenge.

Governments worldwide are indeed taking steps to enhance the security and resilience of critical infrastructure through various regulations.[7] These efforts are crucial to bolstering cyberdefences. The introduction of new laws and regulations also brings challenges, however, such as the potential for overlapping or inconsistent requirements across different jurisdictions, which can complicate compliance and implementation.[8] To combat cyberthreats effectively, a broader multifaceted approach is essential. This approach should include updating and harmonizing legal frameworks across jurisdictions to close regulatory gaps and ensure consistent global enforcement of cybersecurity standards. Fostering international collaboration is critical, requiring coordinated efforts between governments, international organizations and the private sector to share intelligence, establish common protocols and respond swiftly to cyberincidents. Involvement from industries is equally important, as they are often the first line of defence against cyberattacks. Furthermore, harnessing the potential of AI for defence involves investment in AI-driven threat detection systems, automating responses to cyberincidents and developing machine learning algorithms that can adapt to emerging threats in real time. By integrating these elements, such a strategy will not only fortify critical infrastructure but also anticipate and mitigate future cyberthreats in a rapidly evolving technological landscape.

Shifting the cybersecurity posture from one of reaction to proactive, cooperative and holistic defence is essential. This involves anticipating threats before they are manifested, fostering information sharing across borders and industries, and developing adaptive strategies leveraging technological advances. For example, AI and machine learning are increasingly being used to detect threats in real time by analysing vast amounts of data for unusual patterns of behaviour, as seen in platforms like Darktrace and CrowdStrike. These technologies enable faster detection and response to cyberattacks. Additionally, automated incident response systems such as SOAR (Security Orchestration, Automation, and Response) allow the automation of responses to detected threats, improving response times and reducing human error. By implementing such measures, vital systems can be better protected, ensuring their resilience and maintaining the continued stability of an increasingly interconnected world.

A global cooperative cybersecurity framework

Developing a comprehensive global cybersecurity framework that encompasses strategic, legal and technical aspects is imperative to address the ever-evolving cyberthreat landscape. This framework must be designed to ensure robust cybersecurity measures while promoting international cooperation and the adoption of advanced technologies.

First, the framework should implement robust cybersecurity measures and include comprehensive updates and enforcement of international laws. This will involve the establishment of common grounds for the application of international law and clarifying how it applies to the behaviours of different actors in cyberspace. By creating a unified legal approach, nations can better coordinate their efforts to deter and respond to cyberthreats.

Moreover, the legal regulations within this framework must facilitate international cooperation and interoperability across various sectors. Encouraging the adoption of advanced technologies is crucial to staying ahead of cyber adversaries. Legal measures should focus not only on addressing immediate vulnerabilities but also on promoting an environment of continuous improvement and learning. This will include laying the groundwork for enhanced encryption, authentication, biometrics, analytics and automated network security.

Public–private cooperation must be a cornerstone of this framework. Enhanced collaboration in cyberthreat intelligence sharing is essential. Protecting critical technologies such as cloud computing and data centres requires a joint effort between governments and the private sector. Legal regulations should foster such cooperation, ensuring that both parties are equipped to share information and resources effectively.

Resilience must also be a key focus. This can be achieved through targeted investments, partnerships and international cooperation. Enhancing the resilience of critical infrastructure allows better preparation to withstand and recover from cyberattacks. Laws should support these efforts by encouraging investment in cybersecurity measures and promoting collaboration between nations and industries.

Another critical component is improving the investigation and prosecution of cybercrimes, particularly ransomware attacks and targeting illicit cryptocurrency exchanges. Effective legal frameworks should equip law enforcement agencies with the necessary tools and resources to track, apprehend and prosecute cybercriminals. This will include enhancing cross-border cooperation and establishing clear protocols for investigating cybercrimes.

In addition, a concerted effort must foster an environment of innovation and technological advancement within cybersecurity. This will involve investing in cutting-edge research and development and ensuring that there are pathways for the swift adoption and implementation of new technologies. Educational initiatives and training programmes are essential to cultivate a skilled workforce in the latest cybersecurity techniques and methodologies.

Another important aspect is the establishment of global standards and best practices. Organizations and nations can ensure a cohesive and unified defence against cyberthreats by developing and adhering to universally accepted cybersecurity protocols. These standards should be continuously reviewed and updated to reflect the latest technological advances and emerging threats.[9]

Finally, promoting a culture of cybersecurity awareness and responsibility at all levels of society is crucial. Public awareness campaigns, industry-led initiatives and government policies should all aim to educate individuals and organizations about cybersecurity's importance and their role in maintaining a secure digital environment.

A coordinated and multifaceted approach

Developing this comprehensive global cybersecurity framework is not only necessary but urgent. The complexity and scale of cyberthreats require a coordinated and multifaceted approach that leverages the strengths of all the involved stakeholders. Through strategic, legal and technical collaboration a robust defence system can be built to protect critical infrastructure and ensure the stability and security of an interconnected world.

To build an effective global cooperative cybersecurity framework, it is essential to establish clear priorities that address the multifaceted nature of cyberthreats and the diverse needs of the stakeholders involved. These priorities should encompass a range of strategic, technological and collaborative efforts to enhance global cybersecurity resilience.

A priority should be to identify and continuously monitor the evolving threat landscape state actors and advanced criminal hacking groups pose. Understanding these adversaries' tactics, techniques and procedures is crucial for developing proactive defence mechanisms. This requires a robust intelligence-gathering infrastructure, supported by international collaboration, to share insights and threat intelligence in real time.

Securing critical infrastructure through the adoption of new technologies is another vital aspect. This includes the modernization of security architectures and the adaptation of strategies based on security by design principles. By integrating security measures at the inception of system development rather than as an afterthought, inherently secure infrastructure can be created, making it more resistant to attacks.

Advanced encryption and biometric technologies should also be a focus. Developing quantum-proof encryption methods and keyless authentication systems will be essential in safeguarding sensitive data against future threats posed by advances in quantum computing. These technologies will provide robust protection for communication channels and critical data repositories.[10]

The further development and deployment of AI technologies are crucial for real-time horizon scanning and network monitoring. AI can significantly enhance our ability to detect and respond to emerging

threats by analysing vast amounts of data at unprecedented speeds. This will enable more effective threat detection, rapid response and mitigation strategies.[11]

Access and identity management aligned with Zero Trust guidelines should be prioritized to ensure that only authenticated and authorized users can access critical systems and data. Implementing strict access controls and continuous verification processes will minimize the risk of unauthorized access and potential breaches.

Endpoint protection must also be addressed, particularly in the context of the Internet of Things (IoT) and hardware security vulnerabilities. IoT refers to the vast network of interconnected devices – ranging from smart home appliances to industrial sensors – that communicate and exchange data via the internet. These devices often lack robust built-in security, leaving them susceptible to cyberattacks. Securing these endpoints has become increasingly complex with the proliferation of connected devices. Employing comprehensive endpoint protection strategies will help safeguard against threats targeting these devices and the networks to which they are connected.

Cooperative cyberincident response mechanisms are essential for effectively managing and mitigating the impact of cyberincidents. Establishing protocols for coordinated responses across borders and sectors will enhance our ability to contain and resolve incidents swiftly, minimizing damage and facilitating recovery.

Fragmentation of current efforts

While numerous initiatives and collaborations are already making significant progress, the need for a more strategic and cohesive approach remains evident. The fragmented nature of current efforts often leads to inefficiencies and gaps in our collective cybersecurity defences. It is imperative to consider adopting a more centralized approach to address the growing cybersecurity threats and limitations our existing cybersecurity strategies and governance structures pose. While achieving consensus on such a framework at the United Nations level may be challenging because of varying member state interests, and NATO and the EU do not encompass all nations, bringing together stakeholders from governments, academia, industry and international organizations is crucial. This diverse coalition can help coordinate efforts without imposing unwanted oversight, respecting participating entities' sovereignty and

operational independence. The establishment of an international agency transcending the boundaries of existing transnational organizations and supranational structures such as the European Union, the G7 and NATO is therefore a compelling proposal.

This approach requires the fostering of a spirit of collaboration where stakeholders voluntarily share information, best practices and resources. Establishing forums and platforms for regular dialogue and cooperation will facilitate this process, ensuring that all parties remain engaged and committed to the collective goal of enhancing global cybersecurity resilience.

A centralized international agency would serve as a focus for global cybersecurity efforts, facilitating deeper international cooperation among Western allies. This enhanced collaboration is pivotal to address the complexities of modern cyberthreats, which often transcend national borders and require a coordinated response. Such an agency could harmonize policies, standardize best practices and ensure a rapid unified response to emerging threats. Furthermore, this proposed approach would enhance the protection of critical infrastructure and bolster societal resilience and national security. A more robust defence mechanism could be created by fostering deeper cooperation among like-minded Western allies, leveraging participating nations' collective strengths and resources. This would enable a more comprehensive understanding of the cyberthreat landscape, as the international agency could provide a clearer picture of adversaries' tactics, techniques and procedures by pooling intelligence and resources. This collective intelligence would be invaluable in developing proactive defence strategies and staying ahead of evolving threats.

The centralized agency could also play a crucial role in advancing research and development in cybersecurity. By coordinating efforts across nations and industries, innovation and the adoption of cutting-edge technologies could be driven forward, enhancing current defences and preparing for future challenges, ensuring resilience in the face of rapidly evolving cyberthreats.

The agency would also facilitate improved incident response and crisis management. A centralized entity responsible for coordinating responses to cyberincidents could ensure a more efficient and effective reaction to major breaches and attacks. This would involve technical mitigation and strategic communication and recovery efforts, minimizing the impact on affected sectors and populations.

A global cybersecurity framework

The necessity for a comprehensive global cybersecurity framework has become increasingly evident in today's interconnected and technology-dependent world. The vulnerabilities exposed by recent cyberattacks such as those on ViaSat's KA-SAT satellite network during the ongoing conflict in Ukraine underscore the critical need for robust and coordinated cybersecurity measures. These incidents have highlighted the fragility of communications networks and the profound ripple effects that disruptions can cause across geopolitical, social, economic and psychological domains.

The transformation of the communications industry over the last 25 years into a complex interconnected network of terrestrial, satellite and wireless systems further amplifies the importance of securing this infrastructure. The private sector, which owns and operates most of it, bears significant responsibility for its protection. However, the complexity and scale of modern cyberthreats necessitate a collaborative approach, involving both the private sector and governments.

The proposed global cybersecurity framework should prioritize the identification and monitoring of evolving threats, securing critical infrastructure with new technologies, and modernizing security architectures. Advanced encryption, biometric authentication, AI-driven threat detection and adherence to Zero Trust principles in access and identity management should be emphasized. Additionally, comprehensive endpoint protection and cooperative cyberincident response mechanisms are essential to address the vulnerabilities associated with IoT and other emerging technologies.

Public-private cooperation is crucial for effective cybersecurity. Enhanced collaboration in threat intelligence sharing, protection of critical technologies and investments in resilience measures will strengthen collective defences. Legal frameworks must evolve to facilitate international cooperation, promote continuous improvement and support the adoption of advanced security measures.

The establishment of a centralized international agency dedicated to cybersecurity, transcending existing structures such as the European Union, G7 and NATO, would provide a unified strategic approach to managing cyberthreats. This agency would harmonize policies, standardize best practices and coordinate responses to cyberincidents, leveraging the collective strengths and resources of participating nations and industries.

Moreover, fostering a culture of cybersecurity awareness through educational initiatives and training programmes is essential. Equipping professionals with the necessary skills and promoting a collective sense of responsibility will contribute to a more resilient cybersecurity posture.

The path forward requires a multifaceted and proactive approach. International cooperation and innovation can flourish by integrating strategic, legal and technical elements into a cohesive global framework – and allowing scope for tailored national responses. This will help protect critical infrastructure and ensure the stability and security of the digital world. Such an approach will enable the effective anticipation and mitigation of cyberthreats, safeguarding societies and economies against the challenges of the evolving cyber landscape.

Endnotes

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Similarly, ENISA is actively refining governance frameworks to implement national cybersecurity strategies, ensuring they adapt to new challenges: <https://www.nist.gov/news-events/news/2024/08/nist-releases-first-3-finalized-post-quantum-encryption-standards>; <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/topics/national-cyber-security-strategies/national-cyber-security-strategies-guidelines-tools>.

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